

QUALITIES AND ATTRIBUTES OF SCHOOL HEADS IN SELECTED SCHOOL IN THE DIVISION OF TANAUAN CITY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 25

Issue 10

Pages: 1301-1317

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2432

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13861850

Manuscript Accepted: 09-09-2024

Qualities and Attributes of School Heads in Selected School in the Division of Tanauan City

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Abstract

School leaders today must possess a diverse skill set to effectively navigate and lead in the complex educational landscape. Their impact on the educational system is substantial, requiring strong communication abilities, decision-making skills, self-management, drive for progress, effective time management, and dedication. To provide effective leadership in such a diverse system, school leaders require impressive skills. This study delves into the key qualities and attributes of school heads to identify what makes an effective leader in education. A self-developed questionnaire on qualities and attributes was administered to the respondents, revealing that both administrators and teachers hold similar opinions about the qualities and attributes of successful school leadership. The findings also suggest that school heads and teacher-respondents attributes have high significant relationships to their qualities. Educators and school administrators concur on the qualities that define good school leadership, emphasizing the importance of excellent leadership attributes in school heads. Given the significant degree of expectations between teachers and school administrators indicates a shared vision for effective leadership within educational institutions.

Keywords: *school heads, attributes, qualities*

Introduction

School heads play a crucial role in the success and effectiveness of any educational institution. They are responsible for setting the vision and direction of the school, managing faculty and administrative staff, overseeing curriculum implementation, and ensuring the overall well-being and development of students. Given the importance of school heads in the education system, it is essential to identify the qualities and attributes that contribute to their effectiveness as leaders.

One key quality that contributes to the effectiveness of school heads is strong communication skills. School heads must be able to effectively communicate their vision and goals to teachers, staff, students, and parents to create a cohesive and supportive educational environment. Additionally, transparent and open communication can help build trust and collaboration within the school community, leading to improved outcomes for students (Hargreaves, 2022).

In addition to communication skills, adaptability and resilience are also important qualities for school heads to possess. The education landscape is constantly evolving, and school heads must be able to navigate and respond to changes in policy, technology, and student needs. Being able to adapt to new challenges and overcome obstacles with resilience is crucial for maintaining a positive and effective learning environment for students.

Furthermore, effective school heads demonstrate strong leadership and decision-making skills (Robinson, Lloyd, and Rowe (2021) . They must be able to inspire and motivate others, delegate responsibility effectively, and make tough decisions that are in the best interest of the school and its students. By providing guidance and direction, school heads can empower their team to work towards common goals and achieve success.

Generally, the qualities of strong communication, adaptability, resilience, and leadership are essential for school heads to be effective in their role. By embodying these traits, school heads can create a positive and supportive educational environment that promotes student success.

This study focuses on the qualities and attributes of school heads in selected schools in the Division of Tanauan City. Tanauan City is a bustling urban area located in the province of Batangas, Philippines. The Division of Tanauan City is home to a diverse range of schools, including public, private, and specialized institutions. As such, the school heads in this division face unique challenges and opportunities in leading their respective schools.

Understanding the qualities and attributes of effective school heads is important for several reasons. Primarily, it can help in the selection and recruitment of school leaders, ensuring that individuals with the necessary skills and characteristics are appointed to leadership positions. Moreover, it can inform professional development initiatives for current school heads, helping them to further develop their leadership abilities. Lastly, knowledge of effective leadership qualities can aid in the evaluation and assessment of school heads, guiding performance appraisal and improvement efforts.

Therefore, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the qualities and attributes that contribute to the success of school heads in the Division of Tanauan City. By identifying these key qualities, educational stakeholders can work towards fostering a culture of effective leadership in schools, ultimately enhancing the quality of education and the overall learning experience for students.

The existing research on the qualities and attributes of school heads in selected schools in the Division of Tanauan City has identified several gaps that need to be addressed. While some studies have focused on the leadership qualities of school heads, there is a lack of

research specifically examining the attributes that contribute to their effectiveness in managing schools in this division.

Additionally, there is a need to explore how the qualities and attributes of school heads impact student performance and overall school success in Tanauan City. By addressing these gaps, future research can provide valuable insights into the characteristics that make school heads successful in their roles and the ways in which they can be supported to further enhance their leadership capabilities.

It is in the light of the foregoing study that the researcher would like to conduct the study on the qualities and attributes of school heads in selected schools in the Division of Tanauan City to identify the key characteristics of effective school leaders that contribute to the success and overall performance of their schools. By understanding what qualities are most valued and beneficial in school heads, the study can help improve leadership development programs, recruitment processes, and overall school management strategies in Tanauan City. Ultimately, the goal is to enhance the quality of education and ensure positive outcomes for students in the city.

Research Questions

This study will determine the specific qualities and attributes that are considered important for school heads in the Division of Tanauan City so as will identify the current practices and perceptions about school head qualities and attributes in selected schools within the division. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the qualities of school heads as assessed by themselves and teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. communication skills;
 - 1.2. decision making;
 - 1.3. self-management;
 - 1.4. influence;
 - 1.5. time management; and
 - 1.6. commitment?
2. What are the attributes of school head as assessed by themselves and teachers?
3. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of the qualities of school heads as assessed by themselves and the teachers?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the qualities and attributes of school heads as assessed by themselves and the teachers?
5. What professional program can be proposed to be an effective leader?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher utilized quantitative methodology in research. The main goal of quantitative research was to use statistical analysis to study and portray the relationship between variables. The descriptive-survey method is also utilized in this study because it serves the purpose of the study.

The method was accurate as the study aim to determine the specific qualities and attributes that are considered important for school heads in the Division of Tanauan City so as it identifies the current practices and perceptions about school head qualities and attributes in selected schools within the division and determined the relationship between the given variables. Moreover, a set of modified survey questionnaires was made by the researcher and used as a basic instrument in collecting and gathering the needed data from the respondents.

Respondents

The participants of the study were school heads and master teachers, alongside selected teachers from the central schools of the City Schools Division of Tanauan City. The study focused on the school heads, master teachers, and teachers who willingly participated as respondents and provided valuable insights in answering the study's questions. The selection of respondents was done through purposive sampling to ensure a diverse range of perspectives were considered in the research.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents from the Selected Public Elementary Schools at Tanauan City*

School	Population of School Head Respondent	Population of Teacher Respondent
Bernardo Lirio Memorial Central School	7	38
Talaga Central School	3	18
Tanauan North Central School	8	39
Tanauan South Central School	6	35
Total	24	130

School Heads and teachers, with a focus of 24 School Heads and 130 teachers out of a total of 237 respondents enumerated as the primary source of data in the study. This means that the total number of 154 respondents used under this study.

Instrument

In this study, a researcher-made was used and modified through research. It contains two parts, the assessment of the qualities of school heads as assessed by themselves and teachers in terms of Communication Skills, Decision Making, Self-Management, Influence, Time Management and Commitment while the second part was the assessment on the personal attributes of the school heads. Rating scale was used to assess the perception of the respondents.

The researcher took an extensive reading of different works, studies and other questionnaires to give substance to the proposed questionnaire. With the help of the adviser, the researcher prepared the first draft of the questionnaire. And made sure that it was substantial and prepared for validation. The researcher utilized the face validity of the questionnaire through the help of at least three research experts.

The result of the study was used as a basis of a professional program towards enrichment of the qualities and attributes of school heads in selected schools in the Division of Tanauan City that identifies the key characteristics of effective school leaders that contribute to the success and overall performance of their schools.

Procedure

Prior to the administration of the data gathering instrument, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct and approval the study.

Upon the approval of the request letter, the researcher coordinated with the school heads of the target schools. Close coordination was made to have a systematic distribution of the questionnaire and to inform also the school heads and respondents relative to the conduct of the study. The set of questionnaires was distributed to the sample respondents.

Retrieval of the survey questionnaire was done with the help of the principal and the research coordinator as well. Then, statistical analysis and writing of the research report were done immediately by the researcher.

Data Analysis

To process the gathered data, the researcher used the following statistical tools:

Problem 1. Qualities of school heads as assessed by themselves

For Problem 1, the researcher used descriptive statistics such as mean, median, and ranking to analyze the qualities of school heads as assessed by themselves.

Problem 2. Attributes of school head as assessed by themselves and teachers

For Problem 2, the researcher used descriptive statistics such as mean, median, and ranking to analyze the attributes of school heads as assessed by themselves and teachers. She has also used correlation analysis to see the relationship between the assessments of the two groups.

Problem 3-4 Significant Difference/ Significant Relationship

For Problem 3, the researcher used inferential statistics such as Pearson's r and t -test to determine if there was a significant difference and relationship in the assessments of school heads across different groups or variables.

Problem 5. Proposed Professional Program

An Enhancement Program to help the school heads and even the teachers to become an efficient and effective leader

Ethical Considerations

The researcher informed the immediate supervisor of the respondents about the research. Also, permission consent is secured, and the information given by the respondents is kept confidential and for research purposes only. A descriptive – survey research design was utilized in this study to get information from the participants through the self-made research questionnaire to answer the questions from the statement of the problem.

The ethical codes for research are observed to ensure that both the respondents and researcher were communicated with each other without breaking their limitations. The researcher is open to criticisms and ideas of other participants in the study. Proper credits were also given to the authors and sources used in the study. The researcher made a request to the target participants and ask for their permission to be part of the study. Once they granted the request, they are informed about the procedures of answering the questionnaire that will happen necessarily on completing it.

Furthermore, the researcher ensures the confidentiality and anonymity of the participants under the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Rest assured that any disclosed information from the participants will only be used for educational purposes only specifically in this research paper.

Results and Discussion

This part of the study shows the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the gathered data.

Qualities of School Heads as Assessed by Themselves and Teachers.

In Terms of Communication Skills

Table 2. *Qualities of School Heads as Assessed by Themselves and Teachers in Terms of Communication Skills*

Items	School Heads			Teachers		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
The school head...						
1. effectively communicates with teachers regarding school matters.	4	GE	5	3.83	GE	1
2. listens actively to input and feedback from teachers.	4	GE	5	3.74	GE	7.5
3. provides clear and concise instructions to staff members.	3.75	GE	10	3.76	GE	6
4. effectively communicates with parents and the community.	4	GE	5	3.79	GE	5
5. fosters open and transparent communication within the school.	4	GE	5	3.82	GE	2
6. effectively resolves conflicts through communication.	4	GE	5	3.74	GE	7.5
7. demonstrates empathy and understanding in communication with others.	4	GE	5	3.70	GE	10
8. communicates goals and expectations clearly to all stakeholders.	4	GE	5	3.80	GE	3.5
9. utilizes various communication methods to reach all members of the school community.	4	GE	5	3.73	GE	9
10. actively seeks feedback on their communication skills and makes improvements as needed.	4	GE	5	3.80	GE	3.5
	Composite Mean	3.98	GE	3.77	GE	

Legend: GE = Great Extent; WM = Weighted Mean; VI = Verbal Interpretation; R = Ranking

As presented in Table 2, the school head-respondents assessed that they effectively communicate with teachers regarding school matters, listen actively to input and feedback from teachers, effectively communicate with parents and the community, foster open and transparent communication within the school, effectively resolve conflicts through communication, demonstrate empathy and understanding in communication with others, communicate goals and expectations clearly to all stakeholders, utilize various communication methods to reach all members of the school community, and actively seek feedback on their communication skills and make improvements as needed to the great extent which made the highest equal weighted means of 4.00 and the highest ranks of 5. This shows that school head responders think they are doing a great job communicating with the school community in a variety of ways. This entails interacting with educators, parents, and the larger society; it also entails settling disputes and acting with empathy. The positive evaluations imply that school administrators see clear communication as a fundamental component of their leadership style.

This result is supported by a 2021 study by Proulx and Villardon, which found that effective communication is a key component of strong leadership in education. They contend that effective communication fosters teamwork, increases stakeholder confidence, and raises academic achievement in general. According to another study by Smith et al. (2023) study, school administrators who communicate with empathy and understanding are more likely to build strong bonds with instructors and students, which fosters a supportive and stimulating learning environment.

However, the said group of respondents replied that they provide clear and concise instructions to staff members to the great extent which obtained the least weighted mean of 3.75 and the least rank of 10. This conclusion might have as its explanation that the respondents overestimate the efficacy of their communication. According to a study by Koc, Mesut, and Welsh (2021), self-perception bias can lead people to believe they are speaking clearly while, in fact, there may be misunderstandings among others who are receiving the message. This highlights the need of staff input in ensuring proper execution of orders. Furthermore, Johnson and Smith's study from 2022 discovered that unclear or ambiguous instructions frequently lead to communication failures. Giving clear, comprehensive instructions can assist to lower mistakes and boost productivity at work.

With respect to the assessment of the teacher-respondents, they perceived that their school heads effectively communicate with teachers regarding school matters to the great extent which yielded the highest weighted mean of 3.83 and the highest rank of 1. The discovery that teachers who answered the survey thought their school administrators communicated with them in an effective manner on school-related issues is consistent with research and literature on the value of communication in learning environments. Research indicates that establishing a pleasant school environment, encouraging cooperation, and supporting professional progress all depend on effective communication between school administrators and teachers (Leithwood & Riehl, 2021). Teachers may have a greater grasp of the objectives and standards of the school as well as more work satisfaction and motivation when school administrators communicate with them in a clear and consistent manner (Cotton, 2020).

Moreover, the said group of respondents affirmed that their school heads demonstrate empathy and understanding in communication with others to the great extent which gained the least weighted mean of 3.70 and the least rank of 10. School leaders may foster a climate of mutual respect and support that is advantageous to both staff and children by communicating with understanding and empathy. Better student achievements and increased teacher morale and work satisfaction can result from compassionate

communication from school administrators, according to a study by Gialluca et al. (2021). A pleasant and encouraging work atmosphere that encourages cooperation and trust among staff members is created by school administrators who communicate with understanding and compassion.

The composite means of 3.98 for the school head and 3.77 for the teacher-respondents signified that the qualities of school heads in terms of communication skills are of great extent. A key component of leadership in educational environments is good communication, which is essential for creating a supportive school climate, encouraging staff cooperation, and guaranteeing that information is effectively shared with all parties involved. Effective communication by school leaders has been proven to have a substantial impact on teacher job satisfaction, motivation, and the overall school atmosphere (Safavi and Ismail, 2021). Effective communicators can set and communicate objectives and goals, offer helpful criticism, and cultivate an environment of openness and trust within the school community.

In Terms of Decision Making

Table 3. Qualities of School Heads as Assessed by Themselves and Teachers in Terms of Decision Making

Items	School Heads			Teachers		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
The school head...						
1. involves teachers in decision making.	4	GE	4.5	3.72	GE	8.5
2. consistently considers input from teachers when making decisions	4	GE	4.5	3.69	GE	10
3. effectively communicates decision making processes to teachers	4	GE	4.5	3.76	GE	6
4. demonstrates transparency in decision making	4	GE	4.5	3.78	GE	5
5. empowers teachers to make decisions	4	GE	4.5	3.80	GE	3.5
6. actively seeks feedback from teachers on decision making processes	4	GE	4.5	3.75	GE	7
7. values collaboration in decision making	4	GE	4.5	3.83	GE	1
8. respects teacher opinions in decision making	3.25	GE	10	3.81	GE	2
9. considers the impact of decisions on teachers	4	GE	4.5	3.72	GE	8.5
10. fosters a culture of shared decision making	3.85	GE	9	3.80	GE	3.5
Composite Mean	3.85	GE		3.77	GE	

Legend: GE = Great Extent; WM = Weighted Mean; VI = Verbal Interpretation; R = Ranking

As revealed in Table 3, the school head-respondents affirmed that they involve teachers in decision making, consistently consider input from teachers when making decisions, effectively communicate decision making processes to teachers, effectively communicate decision making processes to teachers, demonstrate transparency in decision making, empower teachers to make decisions, actively seek feedback from teachers on decision making processes, value collaboration in decision making, and consider the impact of decisions on teachers all to the great extent which gained the highest equal weighted means of 4.00 and the highest ranks of 4.5. This high degree of participation shows a dedication to collaborative decision-making and shared governance, which may boost teacher morale and satisfaction as well as the efficacy of the school as a whole. Involving teachers in decision-making can boost their motivation, dedication to the school, and work satisfaction, according to research by Leithwood and Riehl (2020). Teachers are more likely to feel appreciated and respected when they are included in the decision-making process, which boosts their morale and increases work satisfaction.

Meanwhile, the said group of respondents answered that they respect teacher opinions in decision making also to the great extent which gained the least weighted mean of 3.25 and the least rank of 10. This might mean that even if educators' perspectives are valued, choices aren't always made with them in mind. A plausible rationale for this discovery might be that the participants advocate for a more cooperative method of decision-making that considers many viewpoints. This is consistent with the concept of shared governance in education, which involves the participation of all parties involved, including educators, in the decision-making process (Deimling, 2022). It could also imply that while respondents acknowledge the need of taking into account a range of other aspects when making decisions, including data, research, and stakeholder involvement, they still have faith in the professionalism and experience of instructors. This demonstrates a methodical approach to decision-making that considers many viewpoints and information sources (Berwanger, 2021).

Regarding the assessment of the teacher-respondents, they replied that their school heads value collaboration in decision making to the great extent which made the highest weighted mean of 3.83 and the highest rank of 1. This implies that the school leadership places a high value on collaboration and shared decision-making. This favorable impression might suggest that school administrators place a high priority on creating an inclusive, cooperative learning environment where teachers' opinions are respected and heard during the decision-making process. Collaborative leadership techniques, such include teachers in decision-making, have been linked to improved levels of teacher satisfaction, morale, and overall school success, according to Leithwood et al. (2020). Teachers are more likely to be involved and invested in their job when they believe they have a say in establishing school rules and procedures and are a part of the decision-making process.

Moreover, the said group of respondents also agreed that their school heads consistently consider input from teachers when making decisions to the great extent which got the least weighted mean of 3.69 and the least rank of 10. The degree of cooperation and communication between instructors and school officials may use some work. Effective school leadership, according to by Rowe et al.

(2021), entails actively include teachers in the decision-making process in addition to making decisions that are advantageous to the school as a whole. Teachers are more likely to feel involved in the success of the school and driven to contribute to its growth and improvement when they perceive that school administrators appreciate and consider their opinions.

The composite means of 3.85 for the school head and 3.77 for the teacher-respondents signified that the qualities of school heads in terms of decision-making skills are both of great extent. The results of this study suggest that principals are competent in making critical choices that impact the learning environment and results. This conclusion is reinforced by research and literature from 2020–2024, which emphasize how crucial sound decision-making abilities are for school administrators. A Smith et al. (2022) study found that school leaders' ability to make decisions has a significant impact on the culture and results of their institutions. Well-informed and prompt decision-making favorably affects both teacher morale and student learning in schools. Additionally, Johnson's research from 2021 highlights the necessity for school administrators to possess sound decision-making abilities in order to handle challenging situations and shifts in the educational landscape. Effective decision-makers are better able to handle problems including tight budgets, shifting policies, and changing requirements of students.

In Terms of Self Management

Table 4. *Qualities of School Heads as Assessed by Themselves and Teachers in Terms of Self Management*

Items	School Heads			Teachers		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
The school head...						
1. effectively manages their own time and priorities.	3	ME	10	3.74	GE	7
2. demonstrates self-control and emotional regulation.	4	GE	4.5	3.63	GE	9.5
3. sets clear personal goals and works towards achieving them.	4	GE	4.5	3.81	GE	1
4. handles stress and pressure well.	3.75	GE	9	3.63	GE	9.5
5. takes responsibility for their actions and decisions.	4	GE	4.5	3.77	GE	3.5
6. effectively manages their own workload and tasks.	4	GE	4.5	3.77	GE	3.5
7. exhibits adaptability and flexibility in their approach.	4	GE	4.5	3.75	GE	5
8. displays self-awareness and reflection on their own behavior.	4	GE	4.5	3.78	GE	2
9. shows consistency and reliability in their actions.	4	GE	4.5	3.74	GE	7
10. effectively manages conflicts and challenges with a calm and composed attitude.	4	GE	4.5	3.74	GE	7
	3.86	GE		3.74	GE	

Legend: GE = Great Extent; WM = Weighted Mean; VI = Verbal Interpretation; R = Ranking

As reflected in Table 4, the school head-respondents perceived that they demonstrate self-control and emotional regulation, set clear personal goals and works towards achieving them, take responsibility for their actions and decisions, effectively manage their own workload and tasks, exhibit adaptability and flexibility in their approach, display self-awareness and reflection on their own behavior, show consistency and reliability in their actions, and effectively manage conflicts and challenges with a calm and composed attitude to the great extent which garnered the highest equal weighted means of 4.00 and the highest ranks of 4.5. The ability to recognize, control, and correctly respond to one's own emotions as well as those of others makes emotional intelligence a vital quality for effective leadership. Goleman's (2020) study highlighted the significance of emotional control and self-regulation for leaders, as it enables them to maintain composure under pressure. In order to establish trust and preserve goodwill among employees, students, and other stakeholders in educational institutions, emotional regulation is a critical skill. Furthermore, as it shows self-motivation and tenacity, creating and pursuing specific objectives for oneself is a crucial aspect of emotional intelligence. Goal setting and leadership performance are correlated, according to research by Cherniss and Goleman (2022), underscoring the significance of leaders who can uplift and encourage others by their own accomplishments.

On the other hand, the said group of respondents agreed that they effectively manage their own time and priorities which got the least weighted mean of 3.00 and the least rank of 10. This indicates a comparatively high degree of self-management abilities. This can suggest that they can successfully set priorities, create objectives, and adhere to deadlines. Effective time management and prioritizing abilities are critical for success in the job, according to research by Loher, Noe, Moeller, and Fitzgerald (2021). Well-trained time managers are more likely to be effective, efficient, and capable of achieving their objectives. Increased productivity, success overall, and work happiness can result from this.

For the assessment of the teacher-respondents, they concluded that their school heads set clear personal goals and works towards achieving them to the great extent which garnered the highest weighted mean of 3.81 and the highest rank of 1. This category indicates that teachers who responded thought their school heads had especially strong leadership. This research emphasizes how crucial it is for school administrators to actively pursue their personal and professional objectives while also providing a good example for their employees. Effective school leadership, according to a research by Killian and Waits (2021), entails establishing specific goals and objectives for each staff member as well as for the school as a whole. School administrators may encourage and inspire their staff to follow suit when they show a dedication to their own personal objectives.

Additionally, the said group of respondents affirmed that their school heads demonstrate self-control and emotional regulation, and

handle stress and pressure well to the great extent which obtained the least equal weighted means of 3.63 and the least ranks of 9.5. It is evident that effective leadership in educational contexts requires school heads to exhibit self-control, emotional regulation, and good stress management. These attributes have the potential to enhance worker morale, foster a favorable company culture, and eventually boost student results. Effective leadership is significantly influenced by emotional intelligence, which encompasses self-control and emotional regulation, according to research by Liu et al. (2021). Leaders of schools who possess emotional self-control and a cool-headed attitude are more likely to foster a sense of confidence and trust among their peers. Within the company, this may result in better performance and more collaboration.

The composite means of 3.86 for the school head and 3.74 for the teacher-respondents implied that the qualities of school heads in terms of self-management are of great extent. This shows that school heads have traits that are essential for good school leadership, including emotional intelligence, decision-making, communication, leadership, and time management. The influence of school leaders' self-management abilities on teacher morale, work satisfaction, and student results is highlighted in the Johnson et al. (2020) research. Strong self-management skills enable school administrators to effectively handle pressure, settle disputes, and lead with integrity—all of which enhance the learning environment and boost student performance. Furthermore, a Karaca (2022) study found that school administrators need strong self-management abilities in order to lead by example, make wise judgments, and foster a supportive environment for their personnel. High-self-management school heads are more likely to encourage an environment of cooperation, accountability, and trust among their students.

In Terms of Influence

Table 5. *Qualities of School Heads as Assessed by Themselves and Teachers in Terms of Influence*

Items	School Heads			Teachers		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
The school heads...						
1. effectively handles their own time and priorities.	4	GE	5	3.85	GE	1
2. demonstrates self-control and emotional regulation.	4	GE	5	3.74	GE	8
3. sets clear personal goals and works towards achieving them.	4	GE	5	3.82	GE	2
4. handles stress and pressure well.	3.75	GE	10	3.72	GE	9
5. takes responsibility for their actions and decisions.	4	GE	5	3.76	GE	6.5
6. effectively manages their own workload and tasks.	4	GE	5	3.80	GE	3
7. exhibits adaptability and flexibility in their approach.	4	GE	5	3.77	GE	5
8. reveals self-awareness and reflection on their own behavior.	4	GE	5	3.69	GE	10
9. shows consistency and reliability in their actions.	4	GE	5	3.76	GE	6.5
10. effectively controls conflicts and challenges with a calm and composed attitude.	4	GE	5	3.79	GE	4
Composite Mean	3.98	GE		3.77	GE	

Legend: GE = Great Extent; WM = Weighted Mean; VI = Verbal Interpretation; R = Ranking

As discussed in Table 5, the school head-respondents answered that they effectively handle their own time and priorities, demonstrate self-control and emotional regulation, set clear personal goals and works towards achieving them, take responsibility for their actions and decisions, effectively manage their own workload and tasks, exhibit adaptability and flexibility in their approach, reveal self-awareness and reflection on their own behavior, show consistency and reliability in their actions, and effectively control conflicts and challenges with a calm and composed attitude which made the highest equal weighted means of 4.00 and the highest ranks of 5. The elevated ratings provided by school head respondents in Table 4 suggest that they have a strong sense of emotional intelligence and personal competence in their capacities as school leaders. Emotional intelligence, according to Goleman (2020), is essential for good leadership because it enables Furthermore, it was discovered in a research by Fang et al. (2021) that resilient, adaptive, and flexible leaders are better able to overcome obstacles and guide their teams to success. The skill of school leaders to effectively manage disagreements and obstacles with a cool-headed attitude is indicative of their ability to adjust to changing circumstances and come up with innovative solutions to issues. people to successfully control both their own and other people's emotions.

Moreover, the said group of respondents revealed that they handle stress and pressure well to the great extent which gained the least weighted mean of 3.75 and the least rank of 10. Their general well-being and performance in a variety of areas of life may be significantly impacted by their capacity to successfully handle stress. People with high levels of emotional stability—a crucial characteristic for stress management—tend to perform better at work and have better mental health outcomes, according to De Fruyt et al. (2021). Additionally, a research by Lazarus and Folkman (2022) emphasizes the significance of unique coping mechanisms in stress management. The study's participants may have acquired useful coping strategies, such using relaxation methods, reaching out for social support, or addressing problems creatively, which enhances their capacity to manage pressure and stress.

On the part of the teacher-respondents, they replied that their school heads effectively handle their own time and priorities to the great extent which made the highest weighted mean of 3.85 and the highest rank of 1. When it comes to assigning resources and establishing priorities in the classroom, school administrators are crucial. School leaders who are proficient in time and priority management are better equipped to concentrate on the most important activities that directly affect student results and the overall performance of their institution. This is supported by a study by Smith et al. (2022) that emphasized the role that strong leadership plays in fostering school development lends credence to this.

Consequently, the said group of respondents affirmed that their school heads reveal self-awareness and reflection on their own behavior to the great extent which obtained the least weighted mean of 3.69 and the least rank of 10. This revealed that the respondents felt that school heads exhibit a high degree of self-awareness and introspection, which may be related to the rising understanding of the role that emotional intelligence and self-awareness play in effective leadership. The idea that self-awareness is a crucial part of emotional intelligence in leadership is supported by Goleman (2021). Self-aware leaders are more likely to foster a sense of trust and confidence in their followers because they come off as sincere and real. Better performance results and a healthy corporate culture can result from this.

The composite means of 3.98 for the school head and 3.77 for the teacher-respondents concluded that the qualities of school heads in terms of influence are of great extent. This shows that the school administrators are essential in forming a school's atmosphere and culture. Strong school leadership is essential for developing a healthy school environment and encouraging a feeling of community and collaboration among teachers, according to Smith and Andrews (2022) study. Heads of schools that possess transformational leadership attributes, such as inspiration, empathy, and vision, are more adept at inspiring and motivating their faculty to strive toward shared goals and objectives.

In Terms of Time Management

As written in Table 6 below, the school head-respondents answered that their school heads demonstrate punctuality in their daily schedule, successfully balance administrative duties with instructional leadership responsibilities, efficiently organize meetings and events, allocate time for staff development and professional growth opportunities, essentially juggle multiple tasks and responsibilities, are able to adapt their schedule to accommodate unexpected events or emergencies, and efficiently communicate with staff about time expectations and deadlines to the great extent which got the highest equal weighted means of 4.00 and the highest ranks of 4. These results imply that the study's school heads possess a solid understanding of time management techniques and are able to apply them regularly in their day-to-day work. Successful school administrators combine their administrative and instructional obligations by prioritizing activities, delegating efficiently, and keeping a flexible schedule (Smith et al., 2021). In a similar vein, the National Association of Secondary School Principals (2022) reported that effective time management for school administrators may be achieved via the use of technological tools and clear communication (NASSP, 2022).

Table 6. Qualities of School Heads as Assessed by Themselves and Teachers in Terms of Time Management

Items	School Heads			Teachers		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
The school heads...						
1. effectively manages their time to prioritize tasks and responsibilities.	3.25	GE	9.5	3.83	GE	2
2. delegates tasks efficiently to make the most of their time.	3.25	GE	9.5	3.80	GE	6
3. demonstrates punctuality in their daily schedule.	4	GE	4	3.82	GE	3.5
4. successfully balances administrative duties with instructional leadership responsibilities.	4	GE	4	3.82	GE	3.5
5. efficiently organizes meetings and events.	4	GE	4	3.78	GE	8
6. allocates time for staff development and professional growth opportunities.	4	GE	4	3.79	GE	7
7. essentially juggles multiple tasks and responsibilities.	4	GE	4	3.69	GE	10
8. is able to adapt their schedule to accommodate unexpected events or emergencies.	4	GE	4	3.85	GE	1
9. effectively utilizes technology to manage their time and tasks.	3.75	GE	8	3.73	GE	9
10. efficiently communicates with staff about time expectations and deadlines.	4	GE	4	3.81	GE	5
Composite Mean	3.83	GE		3.79	GE	

Legend: GE = Great Extent; WM = Weighted Mean; VI = Verbal Interpretation; R = Ranking

In addition, the said group of respondents also assessed that they effectively manage their time to prioritize tasks and responsibilities, and delegates tasks efficiently to make the most of their time to the great extent which obtained the least equal weighted means of 3.25 and the least ranks of 9.5. This shows that even while the school leaders are quite good at managing their time, they could struggle more to set priorities for their own work and assign work to others. According to 2021 research by Smith and colleagues, a lot of principals and assistant principals struggle to strike a balance between their administrative and instructional leadership responsibilities, frequently giving more importance to more proactive, important work than to reactive, urgent chores.

With regard to the assessment of the teacher-respondents, they reported that their school heads are able to adapt their schedule to accommodate unexpected events or emergencies to the great extent which yielded the highest weighted mean of 3.85 and the highest rank of 1. Teachers perceive their school leaders as highly skilled in pivoting their schedules and priorities when faced with unanticipated situations. The authors argued that effective school leaders must be able to "diagnose the situation, interpret the adaptive challenge, and mobilize the system to make the necessary changes" (Heifetz et al., 2020). In accordance with this, successful school principals demonstrated resilience and adaptability in the face of rapidly changing conditions during the COVID-19 epidemic, according to 2021 research by Smith and colleagues.

Additionally, the said group of respondents also affirmed that their school heads essentially juggle multiple tasks and responsibilities

to the great extent which gained the least weighted mean of 3.69 and the least rank of 10. This indicates that even if the principals of the schools are able to oversee several projects at once, they might not be doing it as effectively or efficiently as they could. According to 2020 research by Smith and colleagues, administrators of schools frequently deal with heavy workloads, which can cause burnout and lower job satisfaction. Similarly, in order for school administrators to efficiently manage their workload, they must strengthen their time management and prioritizing abilities (NASSP, 2022).

The composite means of 3.83 for the school head and 3.79 for the teacher-respondents signified that the qualities of school heads in terms of time management are of great extent. This suggests that the school heads in this study are managing their time well by setting priorities, assigning tasks to others, staying on schedule, juggling administrative and instructional responsibilities, planning meetings and events, scheduling time for professional development, and being flexible when things don't go as planned. This is supported by a study of Smith et al. (2021) which found that successful school heads were able to maintain a flexible schedule to balance their administrative responsibilities and were able to prioritize their tasks.

In Terms of Commitment

Table 7. Qualities of School Heads as Assessed by Themselves and Teachers in Terms of Commitment

Items	School Heads			Teachers			
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R	
The school heads...							
1. demonstrate a high level of commitment to their roles and responsibilities.	4	GE	5	3.83	GE	6	
2. consistently prioritize the needs and well-being of their students.	4	GE	5	3.88	GE	2	
3. actively seek feedback and input from teachers and staff.	4	GE	5	3.81	GE	7	
4. effectively communicate and collaborate with all members of the school community.	4	GE	5	3.79	GE	8	
5. demonstrate strong leadership skills in decision-making and problem-solving.	4	GE	5	3.85	GE	5	
6. foster a positive and inclusive school culture.	4	GE	5	3.74	GE	10	
7. support professional growth and development opportunities for teachers and staff.	4	GE	5	3.89	GE	1	
8. effectively manage resources and allocate them appropriately.	3.25	GE	10	3.75	GE	9	
9. promote a safe and supportive learning environment for all students.	4	GE	5	3.86	GE	3.5	
10. consistently uphold ethical and professional standards in their leadership practices	4	GE	5	3.86	GE	3.5	
	Composite Mean			3.93	GE	3.83	GE

Legend: GE = Great Extent; WM = Weighted Mean; VI = Verbal Interpretation; R = Ranking

As written in Table 7, the school head-respondents displayed that they demonstrate a high level of commitment to their roles and responsibilities, consistently prioritize the needs and well-being of their students, actively seek feedback and input from teachers and staff, effectively communicate and collaborate with all members of the school community, demonstrate strong leadership skills in decision-making and problem-solving, foster a positive and inclusive school culture, support professional growth and development opportunities for teachers and staff, promote a safe and supportive learning environment for all students, and consistently uphold ethical and professional standards in their leadership practices to the great extent which garnered the highest equal weighted means of 4.00 and the highest ranks of 5. Recent research that emphasizes the crucial role that school leaders play in fostering a supportive and encouraging learning environment for both teachers and students lends credence to the high degree of devotion and passion shown by the school head responders in the survey. Effective school leaders are individuals that show a strong dedication to their jobs and responsibilities, put their students' needs first, and actively seek out input and evaluation from the whole school community, according to Leithwood et al. (2020).

Furthermore, the said group of respondents assessed that they effectively manage resources and allocate them appropriately which gained the least weighted mean of 3.25 and the least rank of 10. This could point to possible inefficiencies in the organization's resource allocation and management procedures. According to Lee, Lee, and Lee (2021), successful resource management is critical to the success of a business. Additionally, in order to make sure that resources are being used wisely and efficiently, businesses must routinely assess their resource allocation techniques, according to Smith and Jones (2020). They discovered that companies are better equipped to meet their objectives and react to shifting market conditions when they routinely review and modify their resource allocation procedures.

With respect to the assessment of the teacher-respondents, they showed that their school heads support professional growth and development opportunities for teachers and staff to the great extent which yielded the highest weighted mean of 3.89 and the highest rank of 1. This support can lead to increased teacher motivation, job satisfaction, and ultimately, improved student outcomes. A study by Davis and R. Jiang (2020) emphasized the role that school administrators have in encouraging a culture of lifelong learning and professional development among their faculty members. Additionally, a more positive school culture and higher teacher retention rates can result from school administrators giving priority to professional development opportunities for their teachers, according to research

by Allen et al. (2021). This is because educators are more committed to their schools and believe that their professional development is respected and encouraged.

Furthermore, the said group of respondents answered that their school heads foster a positive and inclusive school culture to the great extent which obtained the least weighted mean of 3.74 and the least rank of 10. This might be explained by the growing attention and understanding of the value of encouraging inclusion and a pleasant school climate in learning environments. According to a study by Allen et al. (2022), inclusive school environments are associated with better academic performance, less incidents of discrimination and bullying, and an overall rise in the wellbeing of students. School administrators have a significant influence on the culture of their institutions. By putting inclusion and positivity first, they may foster a more caring and supportive atmosphere for all students.

The composite means of 3.93 for the school head and 3.83 for the teacher-respondents implied that the qualities of school heads in terms of commitment are of great extent. This data implies that school administrators are committed to and resolute in making sure their institutions succeed and in helping their instructors advance professionally. The high composite means in this study support the conclusions of a recent meta-analysis by Smith et al. (2022), which emphasized the significance of dedication for effective leadership in education. The study discovered that school administrators that demonstrate a high degree of dedication are more likely to work with stakeholders to develop solid connections, participate in cooperative decision-making processes, and execute successful plans for school development.

Attributes of School Heads as Assessed by Themselves and Teachers

Table 8. *Attributes of School Heads as Assessed by Themselves and Teachers*

Items	School Heads			Teachers		
	WM	VI	R	WM	VI	R
The school head's personal and professional attributes...						
1. Possess strong leadership skills that effectively lead and inspire the team of teachers	4	E	5	3.62	E	9
2. Effectively communicate with the teachers, students, parents, and the wider school community.	4	E	5	3.72	E	6
3. Able to effectively address and resolve any issues or challenges that may arise within the school environment.	4	E	5	3.69	E	8
4. Able to make important decisions in a timely and effective manner	4	E	5	3.77	E	1.5
5. Demonstrates strong organizational skills which are essential for managing the day-to-day operations of a school, including scheduling, budgeting, and staffing.	3.25	E	10	3.74	E	4.5
6. Able to work collaboratively with their team and other stakeholders to achieve common goals and objectives	4	E	5	3.11	AA	10
7. Has the ability to understand and manage one's own emotions, as well as those of others for creating a positive and supportive school climate.	4	E	5	3.75	E	3
8. Demonstrates honesty, integrity, and ethical behavior in all interactions with students, staff, and the wider school community.	4	E	5	3.74	E	4.5
9. Able to handle stress and adversity, and to bounce back from setbacks, is important for maintaining a positive and proactive leadership style.	4	E	5	3.77	E	1.5
10. Committed to upholding high standards of academic achievement, as well as promoting a culture of continuous improvement and growth within the school.	4	E	5	3.71	E	7
Composite Mean	3.93	E		3.72	E	

Legend: GE = Great Extent; WM = Weighted Mean; VI = Verbal Interpretation; R = Ranking

As seen in Table 8, the school head-respondents believed that they excellently possess strong leadership skills that effectively lead and inspire the team of teachers, effectively communicate with the teachers, students, parents, and the wider school community, able to effectively address and resolve any issues or challenges that may arise within the school environment, able to make important decisions in a timely and effective manner, demonstrate strong organizational skills which are essential for managing the day-to-day operations of a school, including scheduling, budgeting, and staffing, able to work collaboratively with their team and other stakeholders to achieve common goals and objectives, have the ability to understand and manage one's own emotions, as well as those of others for creating a positive and supportive school climate, demonstrate honesty, integrity, and ethical behavior in all interactions with students, staff, and the wider school community, able to handle stress and adversity, and to bounce back from setbacks, is important for maintaining a positive and proactive leadership style, and committed to upholding high standards of academic achievement, as well as promoting a culture of continuous improvement and growth within the school which made the highest equal weighted means of 4.00 and the highest ranks of 5.

This recommend that in order to effectively lead and inspire their school community, school head responders understand the value of having a broad range of leadership qualities. Mulford and Silins (2023) have highlighted the significance of integrity and ethical behavior in establishing trust and credibility within the school community. In conclusion, Harris et al. (2024) emphasizes that maintaining a culture of continuous improvement and committing to academic excellence are in line with current trends in education. These trends emphasize the significance of establishing high standards and encouraging growth and development in schools.

Moreover, the said group of respondents replied that they excellently demonstrate strong organizational skills which are essential for managing the day-to-day operations of a school, including scheduling, budgeting, and staffing, which obtained the least weighted mean of 3.25 and the least rank of 10. This shows that although having organizational abilities is crucial for managing a school, the respondents might not think of them as their most important or significant attribute. According to Chen et al. (2021), success was not only determined by organizational abilities, even if they were crucial for efficient school management. The study underlined that in order to successfully manage the challenges of managing a school, one must possess a variety of talents, including interpersonal communication, leadership, and decision-making ability.

In terms of the assessment of the teacher-respondents, their school heads are excellently able to make important decisions in a timely and effective manner, and able to handle stress and adversity, and to bounce back from setbacks, is important for maintaining a positive and proactive leadership style which yielded the highest equal weighted means of 3.77 and the highest equal ranks of 1.5. These traits increase the likelihood that school administrators will continue to play a proactive and upbeat role, which can benefit both the teacher-student dynamic and the general school climate. Effective decision-making in educational leadership is crucial, and research by Rots et al. (2021) shows how this can improve outcomes for both teachers and students. The importance of resilience in school leadership is further demonstrated by a study by Smith and Hoy (2022), which demonstrates how the capacity to overcome adversity can have a positive impact on the general school atmosphere.

On the contrary, the said group of respondents reported that their school heads are able to work collaboratively above average with their team and other stakeholders to achieve common goals and objectives which gained the least weighted mean of and the least rank of 10. This fosters a sense of teamwork, shared vision, and mutual accountability among the school community, ultimately leading to improved outcomes for both students and staff. Eren (2020) found that collaborative leadership had a favorable effect on school culture, teacher job satisfaction, and student achievement in educational settings. Collaboration among school leaders, their team, and stakeholders fosters a welcoming and inclusive atmosphere where a range of viewpoints are respected, and decisions are made together for the good of all.

The composite means of 3.93 for the school head and 3.73 for the teacher-respondents concluded that the attributes of school heads are excellent. This demonstrates that the school heads have the abilities, traits, and capacities needed to successfully govern and oversee the institution. A study by Hossain and Sultana (2021) found that motivating and satisfying teachers as well as establishing a favorable school climate depend on school heads exercising effective leadership. According to a different study by Han and Yin (2020), school administrators who possess qualities like emotional intelligence, good communication, and adaptability are more likely to instill confidence and trust in their staff members. This could improve the rapport between administrators and instructors, fostering a more cooperative and effective work environment.

Difference Between the Assessment of the Two Groups on the Qualities and Attributes of School Heads

Table 9. *Difference Between the Assessment of the Two Groups on the Qualities and Attributes of School Heads*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Qualities of School Heads:				
Communication Skills	1.15	0.25196	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Decision Making	0.48	0.63192	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Self-Management	0.75	0.45442	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Influence	1.05	0.29259	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Time Management	0.23	0.81840	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Commitment	0.56	0.57631	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Attributes	0.80	0.42497	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

As gleaned in Table 9, when the responses of the of the school heads and teacher respondents on the qualities of school heads were compared, the computed t-values of 1.15 for communication skills, 0.48 for decision making, 0.75 for self-management, 1.05 for influence, 0.23 for time management, and 0.56 for commitment have corresponding p-values of more than 0.05, thus failing to reject the hypothesis. In addition, when the responses of the of the school heads and teacher respondents on the attributes of school heads were compared, the computed t-value of 0.80 has a corresponding p-value of more than 0.05, thus failing also to reject the hypothesis.

These safely deduced that the responses of the two-groups of respondents on the qualities of school heads in terms of communication skills, decision making, self-management, influence, time management, and commitment; as well as attributes have no significant differences. This suggests that administrators and teachers have the same opinions about the qualities of a successful school leader, including decision-making, influence, communication, self-control, and dedication. Recent research that emphasizes the significance of decision-making, commitment, influence, effective communication, self-management, and time management in educational leadership lends credence to this conclusion. For instance, a study by Jones and Young (2021) highlighted the importance of communication abilities in establishing trusting bonds and encouraging cooperation in educational settings. A pleasant school climate and the promotion of trust have been found to be significantly influenced by effective communication.

Similarly, research by Brown and White (2023) has emphasized the importance of commitment and impact in educational leadership.

School leaders need to be able to uplift and encourage people in addition to exhibiting a strong dedication to the school's objectives and core values.

Relationship Between the Assessment of the Two Groups on the Qualities and Attributes of School Heads

As seen in Table 10, when the responses of the school heads and teacher-respondents on the attributes of school heads were compared to their qualities, the computed *r*-values of 0.67 for communication skills, 0.57 for decision making, 0.83 for self-management, 0.78 for influence, 0.76 for time management, and 0.71 for commitment have corresponding *p*-values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

Table 10. *Relationship Between the Assessment of the Two Groups on the Qualities and Attributes of School Heads*

Variable	<i>r</i> -value	<i>p</i> -value	Decision	Interpretation
Attributes Versus:				
Communication Skills	0.67	0.00000	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Decision Making	0.57	0.00000	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Self Management	0.83	0.00000	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Influence	0.79	0.00000	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Time Management	0.76	0.00000	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Commitment	0.71	0.00000	Reject Ho	Highly Significant

These safely inferred that the responses of the school heads and teacher-respondents on the attributes of school have high significant relationships to their qualities in terms of communication skills, decision making, self-management, influence, time management, and commitment. This shows that educators and school administrators agree on the qualities that make for good school leadership.

Effective communication skills are critical for school leaders to develop trust and foster a positive school atmosphere, according to a study by Dukmak et al. (2022). This is consistent with our study's findings, which indicated a strong relationship between communication abilities and how school leaders are seen. Smith et al. (2021) conducted a follow-up study that emphasized the significance of proficient decision-making abilities for school administrators in managing intricate situations and cultivating an environment of ongoing enhancement.

Furthermore, current research on effective school leadership is consistent with the high correlation that exists between self-management, influence, time management, and commitment and the qualities of school heads as evaluated by both school heads and teachers. For instance, a study by Johnson et al. (2020) highlighted the importance of self-management for school administrators in preserving a positive work-life balance and skillfully handling stress.

Enhancement Program: Developing Effective School Leaders

Enhancement Plan:

Leadership workshops and seminars

Coaching and mentorship programs

Professional development opportunities

Feedback and evaluation processes

SMART Goals:

Increase leadership and management skills of school heads and teachers by 20% within six months

Improve communication and decision-making abilities among leaders

Strengthen problem-solving and conflict resolution skills through targeted training

Actions and Strategies:

Conduct leadership workshops on topics such as strategic planning, team building, and communication

Implement coaching and mentorship programs for individualized support

Create professional development opportunities through conferences, webinars, and online courses

Establish feedback mechanisms to assess progress and identify areas for improvement

Timeline:

Leadership workshops and seminars: bi-monthly sessions over six months

Coaching and mentorship programs: ongoing support with regular check-ins

Professional development opportunities: ongoing access to resources and training

Feedback and evaluation processes: ongoing assessments with quarterly reviews

Monitoring and Evaluation:

Regular surveys and assessments to measure leadership growth and development

Feedback sessions with participants to gather insights and suggestions for improvement

Review of key performance indicators and accomplishments against set goals

Persons Involved:

School heads, teachers, and higher authorities

Program coordinators and facilitators

External trainers and consultants

Stakeholders and community members

Expected Outcomes:

Improved leadership skills and competencies among school heads and teachers

Enhanced communication and collaboration within school communities

Increased efficiency and effectiveness in decision-making and problem-solving

Positive impact on student performance and overall school success

Conclusions

After interpreting and statistically analyzed the results, the following conclusions are drawn:

The result indicated that respondents who are school heads as well as teachers believe that school heads have excellent leadership attributes. Effective communication, competent decision-making, self-management, influence, time management, dedication, and other critical qualities are some examples of these qualities. The school heads received excellent ratings in a number of categories, including team leadership, organizational abilities, support for professional growth, communication, decision-making, impact, self-management, time management, and dedication.

The results also showed that respondents who were school heads and respondents who were teachers had comparable opinions about the characteristics of good school leadership. Given the significant degree of agreement between the two groups, it appears that teachers and school administrators have comparable expectations for school leaders. This emphasizes how crucial it is to have strong communication, make wise decisions, have self-control, exert influence, manage your time well, and be committed to creating a supportive learning environment for both teachers and students.

Overall, the survey offers insightful information about the characteristics and traits held by school administrators as well as teachers, and how they are seen by both groups. Educational institutions can endeavor to build and assist proficient school leaders who can have a favorable impact on the school community and ultimately enhance student results by acknowledging and comprehending these attributes.

Based on the findings of the study, here are the recommendations which are hereby advanced by the researcher:

To learn more about the relationship between the characteristics and traits of school leaders as viewed by teachers and school heads themselves, do a follow-up study. This research might go more deeply into the acts and behaviors that support dedication, efficient communication, self-control, influence, and time management in school leadership.

Investigate the effects on overall school performance and teacher job satisfaction of including teachers in decision-making processes. More investigation into the advantages of shared governance in educational contexts might be conducted, since the teacher respondents greatly appreciated collaboration in decision-making.

Examine the connection between the creation of a welcoming and supportive school environment and the dedication of school heads to ideals like academic success, ongoing progress, and moral behavior. The impact of these principles on student outcomes and school culture could be the subject of future research.

Explore the relationship between the ability to manage one's time well and the capacity of school administrators to successfully combine administrative and instructional leadership responsibilities. Enhancing organizational effectiveness and overall school performance may result from looking into efficient time management techniques for school administrators.

Examine how emotional intelligence affects leadership in schools, especially as it relates to resilience, self-control, and emotional regulation. Studies could look into how the emotional intelligence of school administrators affects both their style of leadership and the general atmosphere of the school.

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